

Comparing the Anaesthetic Efficacy of 2% Lignocaine in Combination with 0.5% Bupivacaine Versus 0.5% Bupivacaine for Inferior Alveolar Nerve Block in Surgical Removal of Bilateral Impacted Mandibular Third Molar: A Prospective Study

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Abstract:-

Aim: The aim of this study was to assess and compare the anaesthetic efficacy of 2% lignocaine in combination with 0.5% bupivacaine in 1:1 ratio versus 0.5% bupivacaine for inferior alveolar nerve block in surgical removal of bilateral impacted mandibular third molars.

Method: 15 patients (18 to 35 years) who meet the inclusive criteria were included in the intergroup comparison study. Based on the anaesthetic modality used in this study two groups (A and B) were made. The Groups were given classical inferior alveolar nerve block injection for impaction surgery i.e., Group A were injected with a freshly prepared solution of 1 ml of 2% lignocaine hydrochloride (without adrenaline) admixed with 1ml of 0.5% bupivacaine on one side for surgical removal of impacted third molar whereas Group B included same 15 patients but this group candidates received 2 ml of 0.5% plain bupivacaine for surgical removal of impacted mandibular third molar on contralateral side. A time interval of 3-4 weeks was given between the two procedures and the following parameters were evaluated the pain on injection, the onset of anaesthesia, the duration of anaesthesia and the hemodynamic parameters were evaluated.

Results: The mean time of onset of anaesthesia in group A and B was (1.466 ± 0.516) minutes and (6.533 ± 0.743) minutes respectively and the mean duration of anaesthesia was (254.87 ± 7.539) minutes and (314.93 ± 20.565) minutes in group A and B respectively.

Conclusion: An amalgamated solution of 2% lignocaine with 0.5% bupivacaine in 1:1 ratio is a better alternative anaesthetic agent as it provides minimal pain on injection, rapid onset, and longer duration of action with stable haemodynamic behaviour.

Keywords:- Anaesthetics, Bupivacaine, Impaction, Inferior alveolar nerve block, Lignocaine.

I. INTRODUCTION

A tooth is called impacted, when it is either partially or fully unerupted or is at a position against bone or soft tissue will result in its eruption unlikely to occur (1). The third molar impaction occurs in about 73% of the youthful grown-ups in Europe (2), and their eruptions occur between 17 years to 21 years of age (3). A lot of literature evidence suggests that the likelihood of female having a mandibular third molar impaction is higher when compared to males (4,5). The mandibular third molar impaction occurs when there is no space or an inadequate space available between anterior border of the ascending ramus of the mandible and distal part of the second mandibular molar tooth. Impacted teeth can remain as asymptomatic or they can be associated with various pathologies such as pericoronitis, caries, cysts, tumours, and sometimes it can even cause root resorption of the adjoining tooth (6,7). Surgical removal of an impacted tooth is assumed to be a painful procedure by the patients and so for their concern pain management during the procedure is of at most importance. Pain is defined as an unpleasant sensation unacceptable by individual and for its control many pharmacological as well as non-pharmacological methods are employed by the clinician. The pain control is achieved by injecting anaesthetic drug or agent locally. The most commonly used agents are lignocaine, articaine, bupivacaine, ropivacaine. (8,9,10).

Lignocaine is classified into an amide group and it is routinely used in dentistry. Its metabolism occurs in liver by microsomal oxidase enzymes to monoethylglycine and its derivatives and it gets excreted from the body through kidneys in which less than 10% of the drug is excreted unchanged form while more than 80% of the drug is excreted as different metabolites. Lidocaine became the first marketed local amide anaesthetic in 1948 and most widely used in many countries. Lidocaine is mostly used with vasoconstrictors which can cause hemodynamic alterations during the surgical extraction of molars, similar to other factors, such as patient anxiety or stress levels. Although the safety of using a local anaesthetic together with a vasoconstrictor has been confirmed in the literature, significant abnormalities have been recorded in blood pressure and heart rate of the patients who had

undergone surgical removal of extraction of third molars. (11)

Bupivacaine (1-butyl-2',6'-piperidylidide) was first synthesized by B. A. Ekenstam (1957). This anaesthetic drug classified as an amide, long-acting anaesthetic agent. Bupivacaine has a longer duration of action as compared to lignocaine because of protein-binding capability and a high lipid solubility nature of drug. The onset of action of the drug varies between 1 to 10 minutes and the duration of action lasts up to 2-9 hours with a half-life of approximately 2.7 hours. It has been documented that the potency of bupivacaine is nearly four times as compared to lignocaine when they are used in equal dosages. However, it should be noted that bupivacaine is four times more toxic than lignocaine (11,12).

Injection of Lignocaine with adrenaline is the most commonly used solution for achieving anaesthesia for impaction surgery. Adrenaline is added to local anaesthetic solution for vasoconstriction, to increase the duration of action of local anaesthetic and to reduce the systemic absorption of local anaesthetic solution (10), adrenaline is contraindicated in systemic diseases like cardiovascular diseases and uncontrolled hyperthyroidism (13,14). However, combining lignocaine and bupivacaine anaesthetic agent in one syringe offers the best effects: rapid onset of lidocaine and the prolonged duration of bupivacaine with stable hemodynamic profile (15,16,17).

Aim of this study is to assess and compare the anaesthetic efficacy of 2% lignocaine with 0.5% bupivacaine versus 0.5% bupivacaine in 1:1 ratio for inferior alveolar nerve block in surgical removal of bilateral impacted mandibular third molars.

II. METHODOLOGY

A total of 25 patients (18 to 35 years) were included in this study after obtaining informed written consent and approval from Institutional Review Board for an ethical clearance. Among 25 patients 10 of them did not report back for surgical removal of impacted third molar on contralateral side. Finally, 15 patients were included in intergroup comparison (Group A and Group B). For study, split mouth clinical trial is planned as it avoids any inter-patient discrepancies which may arise during evaluation of the objective parameters and provides an added advantage to study design i.e. no requirement of control as the patients acts as their own controls. Based on the anaesthetic modality employed two groups (A and B) were made. The Groups were given classical inferior alveolar nerve block injection for impaction surgery i.e., Group A patients were injected with a fresh prepared solution of 1 ml of 2% lignocaine hydrochloride (without adrenaline) admixed with 1 ml of 0.5% bupivacaine on one side for surgical removal of impacted third molar while Group B included the same 15 patients and they were administered 2 ml of 0.5% plain bupivacaine for surgical removal of impacted mandibular third molar on contralateral side. The procedure for Group A and Group B were done in an interval period of 3 to 4 weeks. All parameters were recorded before, during and after

surgery. The patients were under postoperative observation for a period of half an hour and then discharged. All the 15 patients were given a dose of medications for 3 days with appropriate postoperative instructions and patients were recalled for follow up on 3rd, and 7th day postoperatively, sutures were removed on 7th post-operative day.

A. Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged between 18-35 years.
- Patients willing to participate in the study and with informed written consent.
- Patients with bilateral impacted mandibular third molars.

B. Parameters assessed:

- Time of onset of anaesthesia.
- Duration of anaesthesia.
- Pain score at the time of injection
- Hemodynamic parameters: Pulse Rate (PR), Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP), Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP), and Peripheral Oxygen Saturation in blood (SpO₂) pre-operatively, intra-operatively and post-operatively.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis of the data was done using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26 software package (SPSS). Descriptive statistics including frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were calculated for demographic variables and various clinical parameters. Normality of the data was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk test, which revealed that the data significantly deviated from normal distribution. Therefore, further analysis was done using non-parametric tests. The mean rank differences between the 2 groups were compared using Mann-Whitney U test. The level of significance in the present study was kept at $p < 0.05$.

IV. RESULTS

A total of 15 participants who completed the study were included in the analysis. Out of the 15 subjects, 8 were females (53.3%) while 7 were males (46.7%). The mean age (\pm SD) of the participants was 27.07 years.

A. Time of onset of anaesthesia

The mean time of onset of anaesthesia in groups A and B was (1.466 ± 0.516) minutes and (6.533 ± 0.743) minutes, respectively. Hence Group A has early onset of anaesthesia than Group B. The Mann-Whitney test was used and the results were statistically significant with p value of 0.000^* ($p < 0.05\%$). [Refer table 1, fig. 1]

B. Duration of anaesthesia

The mean duration of anaesthesia was (254.87 ± 7.539) minutes or (4.247) hours and (314.93 ± 20.565) minutes or (5.248) hours in groups A and B respectively, hence the duration of anaesthesia was found to be more for Group B as compared to Group A and the results were statistically significant with p value 0.000^* ($p < 0.05\%$). [Refer table 2, fig. 2]

C. Pain on injection

The pain score on injecting local anaesthesia ranged from 2 to 6 (15 patients) mean value is (4.33 ± 1.047) in group A. In Group B the pain score on injection ranged from 3 to 6 (15 patients) mean value is (4.73 ± 0.799) . [Refer table 3, fig.3]

D. Haemodynamic Parameters

Heart rate: The mean pre-operative heart rate was higher among group B (94.33 ± 12.338) compared to the subjects under group A (80.17 ± 3.035) with p value of 0.01* which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05^*$). During the surgical procedure the mean heart rate was found to be similar in both the groups. The mean heart rate of Group A (95.87 ± 2.900) and Group B (95.47 ± 11.351) and the mean difference between the two group was 0.40 with p value of 0.288 ($> 0.05^*$) which is not statistically significant. After the completion of surgical procedure i.e. post operatively the mean value of group A was (94.93 ± 7.096) and Group B was (87.93 ± 5.365) with a mean difference of 7.00 and p value is 0.005* which is not statistically significant. [Refer table 4, fig.4]

• **Systolic blood pressure:** The mean pre-operative systolic blood pressure was higher among Group B (128.466 ± 4.050) compared to the subjects under Group A (123.333 ± 9.875) with p value of 0.261* which is not statistically significant since $p > 0.05^*$. During the surgical procedure the mean systolic blood pressure was found to be higher in Group B (134.200 ± 4.312) than Group A (128.533 ± 5.289) and the mean difference between the two group was 5.666 with p value of 0.007 ($> 0.05^*$) which is not statistically significant. After the completion of surgical procedure i.e. post operatively the mean value of Group B (136.133 ± 5.717) was higher than Group A (124.600 ± 8.483) with a mean difference of 11.285 and p value is 0.000* which is statistically highly significant. [Refer table 5, fig. 5]

• **Diastolic blood pressure:** The mean baseline for diastolic blood pressure was higher in Group B (84.733 ± 4.992) than Group A (78.800 ± 6.120) with mean difference to be 5.933 with p value 0.006 (> 0.05) which is not statistically significant. During the surgical procedure diastolic blood pressure was higher in Group B (91.800 ± 5.544) than Group A (80.133 ± 8.01) with a mean difference of 11.66 with p value .000 (< 0.05) which is statistically highly significant. After the completion of surgical procedure, the mean value was found to be higher in Group B (95.933 ± 7.304) than Group A (76.533 ± 7.84) with mean difference of 19.40 with a p value of 0.000 (< 0.05) which is statistically highly significant. [Refer table 6, fig.6]

• **Peripheral oxygen saturation in blood:** The mean baseline for oxygen saturation was almost similar among the subjects under Group A (98.60 ± 1.765) when compared to subjects under Group B (98.40 ± 0.737) with mean difference 0.20 with p value of 0.123 (> 0.05) (Table 3) which is statistically insignificant. During the surgical procedure oxygen saturation was higher in Group B (98.87 ± 1.457) than Group A (96.60 ± 2.165) with mean difference of 2.27 with p value 0.001 (< 0.05) which is statistically significant. Oxygen saturation remained almost similar between the two groups even after

completion of the procedure with mean difference of 0.40 with p value 0.571. [Refer table 7, fig7]

V. DISCUSSION

Local anaesthesia is defined as a loss of sensation in a circumscribed area of the body caused by depression of excitation in nerve endings or an inhibition of the conduction process in peripheral nerves [10]. In dentistry the local anaesthetics are majorly sub divided into two groups: Ester group which includes cocaine, benzocaine, procaine, chlorprocaine etc. and Amide group which includes lidocaine, bupivacaine, mepivacaine, articaine, prilocaine, etc. An ideal local anaesthetic solution on application provides a complete sensory blockade with an adequate duration of action. The two most commonly used local anaesthetics are Bupivacaine and Lignocaine. Lignocaine has short duration of action which is useful for minor procedures but for extensive minor surgical procedures as well as complicated oral surgical procedures, a long acting local anaesthetic is required for which operating surgeon may prefer to perform the surgery under long-acting local anaesthetic.

The duration of anaesthesia for 2% lignocaine without adrenaline is about 5-10 minutes and 60-120 minutes for pulpal and soft tissue anaesthesia respectively [18]. It also has a rapid onset of action of about 2-3 minutes, whereas 0.5% bupivacaine has a much longer duration of action that is 90-180 minutes and 240- 540 minutes for pulpal and soft tissue anaesthesia respectively [11,19], however the duration of onset of bupivacaine is 6-10 minutes which is more as compared to plain lignocaine. [20,21]. This large difference in duration of anaesthesia and onset of anaesthesia between these two drugs is important to the clinician.

These two amides are often used concurrently to obtain a benefit of more rapid onset of lignocaine and the prolonged duration of bupivacaine [20]. Many formulations include adrenaline, which acts as a vasoconstrictor hence it provides a clear surgical field during the procedure and also reduces the systemic absorption of the drug, thereby prolonging the duration of action and decreases systemic toxicity [10]. But in systemic conditions like cardiac disorders, hypertension, seizures, hyperthyroidism, etc. the use of adrenaline has been limited [10,13,14]. Here the operator prefers to use an anaesthetic solution without adrenaline but sometimes they administer multiple injections of anaesthetic solution to increase the duration of action but this can adversely increase the risk of local anaesthetic toxicity. Therefore, in such cases a mixture of lignocaine with bupivacaine is preferred because it provides a quicker and longer duration of anaesthesia, and at the same time, it can also be used effectively and safely in patients where adrenaline is contraindicated. In this study, we have used an amalgamated mixture of 2% plain lignocaine with 0.5% plain bupivacaine in 1:1 ratio to achieve a better anaesthetic effect and the results were compared with plain 0.5% plain bupivacaine. Our study showed that both bupivacaine and lignocaine are completely miscible in nature, and have a better duration of action. These findings were also stated by other similar studies [20,21].

The miscibility is explained by the pKa's of lignocaine (7.9 pKa) and bupivacaine (8.1 pKa) which are very similar and the fact that both the agents are classified under amide anaesthetic group. The physio-chemical characteristics such as lipid solubility, protein binding and pKa determines the anaesthetic property of agents. The anaesthetic agents which have a high affinity to lipids i.e., highly lipophilic property, due to this nature they easily penetrate nerve membrane, similarly anaesthetic agents which are highly protein bound will show a prolong duration of action as they remain attached at receptor site for a longer time. Thus, explaining the longer duration of action of bupivacaine as it is 90% protein bound when compared with lignocaine which has a 64% protein binding affinity[20,22,23]. It's documented that for amalgamated mixture of bupivacaine and lignocaine (without adrenaline) the maximum recommended dose is 0.18 ml/kg (0.08 ml/lb) of body weight, which shouldn't exceed 12 ml i.e., 45 mg of bupivacaine and 120 mg of lignocaine[10].

In our study a total of 15 patients were included and split mouth design was employed for the surgical removal of bilaterally impacted mandibular third molar. thus, Group A and Group B were formed.

Group A - Patients received an amalgamated solution of 2% lignocaine (1-ml) with 0.5% bupivacaine(1-ml).

Group B - Patients received 2ml of 0.5% plain bupivacaine on the contralateral side.

The two surgeries were performed at an interval of 3-4 weeks. In this study all four types of impaction were included i.e Mesioangular, Distoangular, Horizontal and Vertical, so in this study among 30 impactions the most common type was Mesioangular (30%).

Our observation on Onset of Anaesthesia was early for Group A (1.466 ± 0.516) minutes as compared with group B (6.533 ± 0.743) minutes, and the results shows high statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). The duration of action of anaesthesia was found to be more for Group B when compared with Group A and the results show statistical significance with a p value of $0.000^*(p < 0.05\%)$

Oka S et al. (1997) performed a similar study to investigate the effectiveness of lignocaine-bupivacaine mixed solution and compared it with lignocaine (1:200,000 adrenaline) for dental anaesthesia. They concluded that duration of anaesthetic effect was significantly longer with ligno-bupivacaine mixture was used (70.0 ± 15.0 min) than with lignocaine (1:200,000 adrenaline) alone (45 ± 16.4 min). This result also coincides with our study. [24,25].

Akshay Mishra et al in (2018) conducted a randomized split-mouth double-blind clinical trial to find a suitable anaesthetic combination for prolong and complicated minor oral surgical procedures. In this study Group A received 2% lignocaine with 1:200,000 adrenaline while in group B, amalgamated mixture of 2% lignocaine and 0.5% bupivacaine was used. They concluded that the amalgamated mixture of lignocaine and bupivacaine had equivocally rational onset and provided in-depth anaesthesia

especially in complicated and protracted minor oral surgical procedures. Another variable which was found to be valuable between the two local anaesthetics groups (Group A and Group B) was Post operative heart rate [16]. Our results showed group A had higher post operative mean heart rate as compared to group B but the p value was 0.005, we believe a higher sample size should be employed to get a significant p value.

K. Balakrishnan et al (2014) reviewed the analgesic and anaesthetic abilities of the bupivacaine versus lignocaine for the surgical removal of impacted third molars. It has been found that both bupivacaine and lignocaine have their merits and demerits but it has been proven by the clinical trials that bupivacaine provides better and prolonged anaesthesia during minor surgical procedures. They concluded that bupivacaine can be regularly used as an anaesthetic agent, provided care should be taken regarding the dosage and cardio depressant property of the bupivacaine [18].

The above-mentioned study describes about the cardio depressant property of bupivacaine, but in our study as there was increased mean value of systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure in group B. After the completion of surgical procedure i.e., post operatively the mean value systolic blood pressure of Group B (136.133 ± 5.717) was higher than Group A (124.600 ± 8.483) with a mean difference of 11.285 and p value is 0.000^* which is statistically highly significant. After the completion of surgical procedure, the mean value was found to be higher in Group B (95.933 ± 7.304) than Group A (76.533 ± 7.84) with mean difference of 19.40, p value of $0.000 (< 0.05)$ which is statistically highly significant. We require further studies with large sample size to explain this peculiar result. Our results showed minimum variation in blood pressure and heart rate in group A, thus indicating that amalgamated solution with an equal volume i.e., 1-ml of 0.5% bupivacaine with 1-ml of 2% lignocaine is better.

When minor surgical procedures are of longer duration, the use of amalgamated ligno-bupivacaine solution has a better effectiveness, this combination mixture has many advantages; one is that its time of onset is shorter and relatively less painful during administration by injection [20,25] also in our study we can see that the pain score during injecting local anaesthesia, ranged from 2 to 6 (15 patients) mean value is (4.33 ± 1.047) in group A, while in group B the pain score on injection ranged from 3 to 6 (15 patients) mean value is (4.73 ± 0.799). The other advantages of this amalgamated solution are prolonged anaesthetic duration, good postoperative analgesic effect and in patients where adrenaline is contraindicated. Even though with the proven safety record of amalgamated ligno-bupivacaine mixture, its efficacy still remains undocumented and unexploited in oral and maxillofacial surgical procedures. Thus, for a difficult minor oral surgical procedure we especially recommend the use of lignocaine-bupivacaine mixture as it has shown a beneficial and viable alternative to adrenalized lignocaine anaesthetic [18,21].

VI. CONCLUSION

We conclude that amalgamated solution of 2% lignocaine with 0.5% bupivacaine in 1:1 ratio is a better alternative anaesthetic agent as it provides minimal pain on injection, rapid onset, longer duration of action with stable haemodynamic behaviour in patients undergoing prolonged oral surgical procedures with increased overall patients comfort and cooperation. This mixture has added advantages over conventional anaesthetics but surprisingly its efficacy and effectiveness still remain unexploited and undocumented in oral and maxillofacial surgery.

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TABLES

	LA Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean rank	p value
Onset of Anaesthesia	Group A	15	1.4667	.51640	8.00	0.000*
	Group B	15	6.5333	.74322	23.00	

Table 1: Distribution of mean value of onset of anaesthesia among two groups.

Mann – Whitney test

* statistically highly significant

Fig. 1. Mean value of onset of anaesthesia among two groups.

	LA Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Rank	p value
Duration Of Anaesthesia	Group A	15	254.87	7.539	8.00	.000*
	Group B	15	314.93	20.565	23.00	

Table 2: Mean distribution of Duration of Anaesthesia (in minutes) among two groups

Mann – Whitney test

*statistically highly significant

Fig 2. Mean value of Duration of anaesthesia (in minutes) among two groups

	LA Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pain On Injection	Group A	15	4.33	1.047
	Group B	15	4.73	.799

Table 3: Mean distribution of Pain on Injection among two groups

Fig 3. Mean value of Pain on Injection among two groups

	LA Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Rank	p value
Pre op heart rate	Group A	15	80.07	3.035	10.27	.01
	Group B	15	94.33	12.338	20.73	
Intra op heart rate	Group A	15	95.87	2.900	17.20	.288
	Group B	15	95.47	11.351	13.80	
Post op heart rate	Group A	15	94.93	7.096	19.97	.005
	Group B	15	87.93	5.365	11.03	

Table 4: Mean value of Heart Rate (beats/min) among two groups

Mann – Whitney test

*Pre op heart rate is statistically significant

Fig 4. Mean value of Heart Rate (beats/min) among two groups

	LA Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Rank	P value
Pre Op Systolic BP	Group A	15	123.333	9.87541	13.70	.261
	Group B	15	128.466	4.05087	17.30	
Intra Op Systolic BP	Group A	15	128.533	5.28970	11.17	.007
	Group B	15	134.200	4.31277	19.83	
Post Op Systolic BP	Group A	15	124.600	8.48360	9.67	.000
	Group B	15	136.133	5.71797	21.33	

Table 5: Distribution of Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg) during pre operative ,intra operative and post operative periods among two groups.

Mann-Whitney Test

*post op systolic blood pressure statistically highly significant

Fig 5. Mean value of Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg) during pre operative ,intra operative and post operative periods among two groups.

	LA Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Rank	P value
Pre Op Diastolic BP	Group A	15	78.800	6.12022	11.10	.006
	Group B	15	84.733	4.99238	19.90	
Intra Op Diastolic BP	Group A	15	80.133	8.01665	9.40	.000
	Group B	15	91.800	5.54462	21.60	
Post Op Diastolic BP	Group A	15	76.533	7.84553	8.50	.000
	Group B	15	95.933	7.30427	22.50	

Table 6: Distribution of Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg) during pre operative ,intra operative and post operative periods among two groups.

Mann-Whitney Test

*p < 0.05: statistically significant

Fig 6. Mean value of Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg) among two groups

	LA Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Rank	p value
Pre Op Spo2%	Group A	15	98.60	1.765	17.80	.123
	Group B	15	98.40	.737	13.20	
Intra Op Spo2	Group A	15	96.60	2.165	10.10	.001
	Group B	15	98.87	1.457	20.90	
Post Op Spo2	Group A	15	99.07	1.163	14.67	.571
	Group B	15	99.47	.516	16.33	

Table 7: Distribution of peripheral oxygen saturation in blood SpO2 among two groups

Mann-Whitney Test

*p < 0.05: Intraoperative SpO2 is statistically significant

Fig 7. Distribution of Mean Value of SpO2 among two groups